

ISic1279

Edict of Flavius Felix Eumathus regarding the Thermae Achillianae

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2016.10.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 265

Physical Description

A very wide text laid out across multiple marble slabs of differing widths, of which 8 pieces are preserved (originally 6, but two have become further fragmented over time). The slabs were most likely displayed on the facade of the building to which they relate.

Dimensions

Height 29.5-30.3 cm

Width greater than 469.1 cm

Depth 2.3-4.9 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-4: 44-62 mm

Interlineation

Lines 1-4: 9-27 mm

Text

1. Φλάβιος Φήλιξ Εὐμάθιος ὁ λαμπρ[ότατος] ὑπατικὸς τῆς Σικελῶν ἐπαρχίας εἶπεν· αἱ θερμαὶ αἱ Ἀχιλλιαναὶ ἐξ ἀρχαίας διατυπώσεως ἀνήλ[ωσαν] πῆσας--- καθ' ἐκάστην ἡμέραν---] ἰούσης τῆς ἐπισκευῆς ἐ [πιμελεία] Φλαβίου]
2. Λιβεραλίου τοῦ εὐκαθωσιώτου, ἀνή[λωσαν] ἔλαττον]. [τὸ καπνιστήριον] καθ' ἐκάστην ἡμέραν πῆσας λβ ἔλαττον ἔκαυσεν εἰς τὴν πρόκαυσιν [καίεις τὴν ὑπόκαυσιν ἔλαττον ἔκαυ]σεν πῆσας ιη, ἐ [πο]ίει νο (μίσματα) [---. ὅσον τὸ καπνιστήριον]
3. ἔκαυσεν εἰς τὴν πρόκαυσιν καὶ εἰς τ [ὴν] ὑπόκαυσιν δι' ἡμέρας---, ἔδωκε]ν ὁ προγραφὶς εὐκαθωσιώτος τῶν ε[ἰ]δίων ἀναλωμάτων π [---] το ἐπὶ ὑ (πῆρ) Π

[νομισ]ματ [---]

4. τοῦ ἀρχιτέκτονος· μετὰ τὴν ὑπ[ατείαν τοῦ δεσπότης ἡμῶν Θεοδο]σίου αἰωνίου Αὐγούστου τὸ δι' κ[α]ὶ Μαξίμου τοῦ λαμπ [ροτάτου.]

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen

Translation (en)

Flavius Felix Eumathius, the most distinguished consular governor of the province of Sicily decrees:

The Achillian Baths, in their old configuration, consumed [x pēsas (of wood) daily (?). ...]

following the restoration overseen by (?)Flavius(?) Liberalis, devotissimus, they consumed less. The

furnace(?) burned 22 fewer pēsas each day for the heating and 18 fewer pēsas for the hypocaust, at a

cost of [...].The amount that the furnace burned for the heating and the hypocaust daily [--?], the

aforementioned devotissimus gave at his own expense [---] of the architect [---]. (Decreed) After

the consulship of our Emperor Theododius the eternal Augustus, for the fourteenth time, and the most

distinguished Maximus.

Translation (it)

Flavius Felix Eumathius, illustrissimo governatore consolare della provincia di Sicilia, decreta: le

terme Achilliane secondo il vecchio regolamento consumavano [giornalmente x pesas (di legna) ogni

giorno (?). ...] Dopo la ristrutturazione [avviata da Flavius] Liberalis, devotissimus [consumavano

meno. La fornace (?) ...] ogni giorno bruciava 22 pesas in meno per il preriscaldamento e 18 [pesa

di meno brucia per il riscaldamento ...] per un costo di [---]. La somma che [il forno] bruciava per

il preriscaldamento e per [il riscaldamento giornalmente -----] fornì il soprascritto devotissimus a

proprie spese; [-----](lettere non traducibili) -----]

dell'architetto; (Decretato) dopo [il consolato dell'imperatore

Teodosio] l'eterno Augustus per la

quattordicesima volta e dell'illustrissimo Massimus.

Commentary

The word πήσας is a hapax. It is plausibly explained by Manganaro (1958-1959: 28 n.94) as being a calque in Greek of the Latin word *pensum*, signifying a weight of a fixed quantity. Manganaro additionally observes that in Sicilian dialect the word 'pisa' signifies a specific weight (4 kg) of flour or salt, and suggests that in this text a 'pesa' would be a cord of wood of approx. 5 kg.

The word εὐκαθωσιώτου is also rare: as demonstrated by Manganaro and Korhonen it appears to be a synonym for καθοσσωμένος equivalent to *devotissimus*.

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